

1 Genetic and genomic studies in ovine mastitis

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12 13 **ABSTRACT**

14 Mastitis is a strong financial and animal welfare concern in both dairy and meat-producing sheep.
15 In this review article, we summarized recent advances in research on genomic of mastitis resistance in
16 sheep. Heritability estimates for mastitis-related traits such as somatic cell scores or milk bacteriological
17 counting have confirmed a genetic basis for mastitis resistance. Recent outputs from genomic-based
18 studies comprising genome-wide associations, the identification of one causal mutation as well as gene
19 expression studies have highlighted regions of the genome, and possible genes and mechanisms
20 underlying the resistance trait. Part of genomic regions was common among breeds and populations,
21 and have testified to the partial sharing of mastitis-related genetic mechanisms between different distant
22 dairy sheep populations. Accumulating genetic data, however, have underlined the polygenic nature of
23 the trait and the complexity of the resistance phenotype. Both quantitative and genomic analyses have
24 further revealed trade-offs and synergies under genetic control between mastitis resistance and other
25 efficiency (milk production) and resilience related traits (udder type traits and metabolic disease). We
26 have also reported how phenotypic, pedigree and genomic information has been used in sheep breeding,
27 the aim being to improve the animals' health and welfare, the hygienic quality of milk products and
28 overall efficiency and resilience.

29
30 *Keywords:* genetic resistance; intramammary infections; mastitis; animal genomics; sheep; genetic
31 parameters

32 33 34 **1. Introduction**

35
36 Genetics of mastitis has been studied more recently in dairy sheep (Baro et al., 1994; El-Saied et
37 al., 1999; Barillet et al., 2001; Serrano et al., 2003) than in dairy cattle where it has been increasingly

38 well documented since the 1980s (Emanuelson and Philipsson, 1984; Emanuelson et al., 1988 ; Mrode
39 and Swanson, 1996; Heringstad et al., 2000; Detilleux, 2002; Rupp and Boichard, 2003). In general,
40 relevant studies have focused on dairy sheep, with few data produced in meat or wool production sheep
41 populations.

42 First evidence that a host's response to mastitis was under genetic control, came from quantitative
43 genetic studies and the estimation of genetic parameters for mastitis-related traits. The approach relies
44 on the assumption that the trait is determined by a combination of animal (age, lactation stage, etc.),
45 genetic (breed, line, etc.), and environmental factors, the latter including both microbiological (infection
46 pressure, pathogen species and strain, etc.) and husbandry parameters (breeder practices regarding
47 machine milking, sheepfold, etc.). No assumption had been made about the underlying genes and
48 mechanisms. The heritability parameter quantifies the amount of variability in a given trait that is due
49 to additive genetic values. It also allows the estimation of genetic value for the animals (breeding value)
50 and predicting to what extent a selection process can be efficient. These studies, however, require large
51 data sets with phenotypic information and pedigree. Therefore, the most common mastitis-related trait
52 used in ovine mastitis genetic studies is the somatic cell count (SCC). Indeed, somatic cell counts can
53 be easily measured in milk samples, as an indirect predictor of mammary infection, which is much more
54 frequent than clinical mastitis in sheep (Bergonier et al., 2003).

55 Since 2009, the development of genomic methods and tools applied to sheep have contributed to
56 enhance insights into the genetic control of processes governing host resistance to mastitis. The sheep
57 genome was sequenced in 2007 (Jiang et al., 2014) and several low- to high-density ovine SNP (single-
58 nucleotide polymorphism) chips have been developed as part of the International Sheep Genomics
59 Consortium (ISGC; www.sheephapmap.org) (Kijas et al., 2009). Availability of such tools has enabled
60 genome scans to identify and fine map genomic regions associated with traits (QTL for Quantitative
61 Trait Loci), the gene expression studies to highlight pathways and genes involved in the host's response
62 to infection, and the first use of genome-wide information in sheep breeding.

63 This paper reviews the state of the art on the genetic control of resistance to mastitis, with primary
64 reference to sheep. Genetic parameters for different mastitis-related traits are presented and genetic
65 associations with other traits of interest are discussed. The paper then reports on recent outputs from
66 genomic-based studies comprising QTL detection studies and the identification of causal mutations as
67 well as gene expression studies. Finally, it considers how information using genome-wide information
68 (or not) is currently used in sheep breeding with some discussion on future prospects.

69

70 **2. Genetic parameters of ovine mastitis**

71

72 *2.1. Genetic parameters for mastitis-related traits*

73

74 For three decades, published literature on genetic parameters of ovine mastitis in dairy sheep has
75 been accumulating, as reported in earlier reviews (Carta et al., 2009; Rupp and Foucras, 2010; Riggio
76 and Portolano, 2015). The most common mastitis-related traits used in genetic studies is a logarithmic
77 transformation of somatic cell counts termed ‘Somatic Cell Score’ (SCS) (Ali and Shook, 1980).
78 Heritabilities for somatic cell scores (lactation period average or repeated test day records) have been
79 reported in sheep, as shown in Table 1 **Erreur ! Source du renvoi introuvable.** Heritability estimates
80 are low and range from 0.04 to 0.28 with a weighted average of 0.163 (Table S1 for the explanation of
81 the calculation) for various dairy sheep breeds, including Chios (Greece), Churra (Spain), East Friesian
82 (Germany), Lacaune (France), Latxa (Spain), Manchega (Spain), Manech Red Face (France), Sarda
83 (Italy) and Valle del Belice (Italy). These heritabilities showed that genetic variation existed for this
84 trait, although to a lesser extent than for production traits with heritabilities ranging from 0.30 to 0.60.
85 The California Mastitis Test score is another less used indirect mastitis-related trait based on milk
86 somatic cells. This test consists of the addition in the milk of a reagent composed of a detergent and a
87 pH indicator. When mixed with the milk, the reagent reacts and forms a viscous gel, which can be scored
88 using a range of milk color and viscosity, therefore indicating the number of somatic cells and the level
89 of inflammation. Only one study in dairy sheep (Banos et al., 2017) estimated a heritability for this trait
90 (0.12), which is in the same range as for somatic cell score. However, both somatic cell scores and
91 results of the California Mastitis Test are two indirect measures for mastitis, which reflect the degree of
92 inflammation in the mammary gland rather than infection status. The trait, therefore, combines the
93 measure of severity of infection and intensity of the host’s response. Direct measures of mastitis, e.g.,
94 the occurrence of clinical mastitis based on examinations of veterinarians have been very little studied
95 in dairy sheep, because of the small frequency of the disease (Bergonier et al., 2003) and the difficulty
96 to implement it on a large scale. Heritability of this binary trait (presence/absence of clinical mastitis)
97 has been estimated at 0.18 in the Chios breed (Banos et al., 2017), which is also in the same range as for
98 somatic cell scores.

99 Very recently, studies in meat-producing sheep breeds have estimated genetic parameters for
100 mastitis-related traits, as it is a strong financial and animal welfare concern (Conington et al., 2008).
101 Heritability of occurrence of clinical mastitis was estimated at 0.04 in an Irish population including
102 Belclare, Charollais, Suffolk, Texel and Vendéen breeds (O’Brien et al., 2017). In the Texel breed,
103 somatic cell scores and results of California Mastitis Test estimates of heritability ranged from 0.07 to
104 0.11 (McLaren et al., 2018). Although these heritabilities are somewhat smaller than in dairy sheep,
105 probably due, at least partly, to the recording scheme (only one examination per animal), they have
106 confirmed that, as expected, genetic control for mastitis also exists in those meat-producing sheep
107 breeds.

108 During the last decade, genetic studies have focused on bacteriological analyses of milk samples,
109 in order to better quantify the intramammary bacterial pressure in dairy sheep. The most widely used
110 technique in the dairy sheep literature is a count of bacterial colonies in milk samples after incubation

111 on agar plates. This conventional technique leads to a binary trait of infection status (ewe considered as
112 infected if over 5 colony-forming-units per 10 μ L of milk of one bacterial species would be recovered).
113 Estimates of heritability of this trait termed ‘infection status’ ranged from 0.02 to 0.09 (Table 1) in the
114 Valle del Belice breed (Riggio et al., 2010; Tolone et al., 2013; 2016) and seem to depend on the species
115 of bacteria. One study (Banos et al., 2017) has estimated heritability of another trait based on
116 bacteriological examination of milk samples, the total bacterial count, which refers to the number of
117 viable bacteria per mL of milk. Heritability of this estimate is of the same order of magnitude as the
118 infection trait (0.09), which is lower than heritabilities of the traits based on milk somatic cells. One last
119 technique, recently employed in the French Lacaune breed (Allain et al., 2018) has been based on
120 amplification on staphylococcal DNA by qPCR in milk samples, representing the number of bacterial
121 genomes in 10 μ L of milk. Estimate of heritability of this continuous trait was in the same range as
122 somatic cell scores (0.18).

123 Genetic correlations have also been estimated (Table 1) between the various mastitis-related traits
124 described above. The occurrence of clinical mastitis has been found to be positively correlated with
125 somatic cell scores, results of California Mastitis Test and total bacterial counts (0.35 - 0.36) in Chios
126 animals (Banos et al., 2017), suggesting a common genetic basis between development of disease and
127 the various traits indirectly indicating mastitis. Genetic correlations between the two leucocyte-related
128 traits (results of California Mastitis Test and somatic cell scores) ranged from 0.76 to 0.98 (Banos et al.,
129 2017; McLaren et al., 2018), confirming the usefulness of the California Mastitis Test as an alternative
130 to cell counting. Infectious status (conventional technique) and somatic cell scores have also been found
131 to be highly correlated (0.51 to 0.93) (Riggio et al., 2010; Tolone et al., 2013), as did also total bacterial
132 counts with somatic cell scores (0.56) (Banos et al., 2017) and staphylococcal DNA with somatic cell
133 scores (0.72) (Allain et al., 2018). Milk bacteriological traits seemed then to be genetically close to the
134 most used mastitis-related trait ‘somatic cell score’. These reasonably high values have suggested a
135 commonality of resistance mechanisms that lead to better resistance to either persistent intra-mammary
136 infection (continuously high SCC) or acute clinical episodes with presence of pathogens in the udder,
137 despite the fact that those forms of mastitis might be associated with various environmental conditions,
138 pathogens, and status of the animal.

139

140 *2.2. Genetic relationships of mastitis resistance with other traits*

141

142 *2.2.1. Relationships with milk production traits*

143 Genetic correlation estimates between mastitis-related traits and milk yield trait in sheep are
144 presented in Table 1. These are inconsistent across the various dairy breeds. Indeed, estimates were
145 found to be negative (i.e., favorable) for Spanish and Greek breeds, with genetic correlations from -0.37
146 for Churra to -0.09 for Chios ewes, and positive (i.e., unfavourable) for German, Italian and French
147 breeds, with genetic correlations 0.02 for East Friesian to 0.59 for Valle del Belice ewes. The weighted

148 average of these estimates is 0.078 (Table S1). An explanation for these inconsistent results between the
149 different breeds may simply be statistical reasons. Differences in genetic correlation estimates between
150 Spanish and the other breeds can be due to lower selection pressure applied in the Spanish breeds, or to
151 the fact that estimates in Spanish breeds were mainly obtained considering different lactations whereas,
152 in the other breeds, they mostly considered only the first lactation. Some pleiotropic genes, for example
153 the group-specific component (*GC*) gene, could explain the relation between udder health and
154 production traits. This gene encodes the vitamin D-Binding Protein (DBP) which has multiple roles in
155 immune defense and milk production, as found in cattle (Olsen et al., 2016). Another pleiotropic gene
156 is the *suppressor of cytokine signalling2 (SOCS2)* gene, which has been found to be associated with
157 mastitis in sheep and also had an effect on growth and milk production (Rupp et al., 2015). It also can
158 be due to a selection sweep, when selection for milk production has ‘hitchhiked’ along with it a nearby
159 allele on the chromosome that is associated mastitis susceptibility. Other possible explanations for strong
160 unfavorable genetic correlations are the biological competition between functions for energy and
161 nutrients and the relationship between mastitis and udder type traits.

162

163 2.2.2. Relationships with udder type traits and milking ease

164 A few studies in dairy and meat-producing sheep have dealt with estimating genetic correlations
165 between udder-type and mastitis-related traits (Legarra and Ugarte, 2005; Barillet, 2007; Casu et al.,
166 2010; McLaren et al., 2018). Udder attachment was negatively correlated with mastitis (genetic
167 correlations: -0.27 to -0.42), whereas long teats were favorable for mastitis (genetic correlations: 0.26
168 to 0.44), indicating that ewes with a pendulous udder or longer teats are at greater risk to develop
169 mastitis. Moreover, teat angle has also been negatively correlated with mastitis (genetic correlations: -
170 0.12 to -0.55). One study also has demonstrated the positive genetic relationship between mastitis
171 resistance and milking ease (Allain et al., 2018). Indeed, genetic correlations of somatic cell scores or
172 quantity of staphylococcal DNA in milk with milk flow traits ranged from 0.26 to 0.30 and from -0.04
173 to -0.33 with latency time and real milking time, respectively. These values confirmed that ewes with
174 the higher relaxing ability of the teat muscle (able to quickly release milk) allowed more pathogens to
175 enter into the mammary gland, potentially leading to mastitis.

176

177 2.2.3. Relationships with body, feet type and meat production traits

178 Genetic association of mastitis traits with body conformation, feet type, and meat production traits
179 have been found to be close to zero. Indeed, the estimate of genetic correlation of somatic cell scores
180 with litter size was at 0.001 for East Friesian ewes (Hamann et al., 2004). Estimates with morphological
181 traits, including stature, rear legs, feet angle, rump width, and general body score, ranged from -0.06 to
182 0.11, with high standard errors for Churra ewes (De la Fuente et al., 2011), as well as for meat-producing
183 sheep breeds (O’Brien et al., 2017). These results indicate that selection for one of these traits would not
184 affect susceptibility to mastitis of the individuals.

185

186 2.2.4. Relationship with resistance to other diseases

187 Mastitis is mainly caused by extracellular and facultative intracellular bacteria and the host's
188 resistance probably involves a crucial role of the type-1 immune response. However, the control of
189 parasites is predominately governed by a type-2 immune response. Also, there is evidence that different
190 components of the immune response, including type-1 and type-2 responses, and resistance to various
191 diseases, show null to antagonistic genetic correlation (Mouton et al., 1984; Pinard-van der Laan, 2002;
192 Crawley et al., 2005). In sheep, a link between mastitis resistance with resistance to gastrointestinal
193 nematodes was reported in an experiment, in which sheep divergently selected for either high or low
194 somatic cell counts received an oral challenge with *Haemonchus contortus* (Traoré et al., 2008).
195 Whereas lambs showed highly variable response to challenge, there was no difference between the
196 genetic lines, which suggested that genetic resistance to either mastitis or gastrointestinal nematodes
197 were under independent genetic regulations.

198 The link of mastitis resistance to metabolic disease was addressed in an experiment, in which
199 sheep divergently selected for either high or low somatic cell counts, received an energy-restricted diet
200 (Bouvier-Muller et al., 2016; 2018). The authors showed that sheep from the low cell count line, which
201 were less susceptible to mastitis, were also less susceptible to ketosis in early lactation (identified by
202 measurements of concentrations of β -hydroxybutyrate and non-esterified fatty acids in blood). They
203 concluded that these positive correlations suggested some commonalities in genetic control of immune
204 response and energy metabolism, but may also reflect indirect associations due to competition for
205 nutrients.

206 Finally, a question was put forward whether resistance to mastitis was independent to resistance
207 to other microbial diseases of sheep, e.g., footrot, paratuberculosis or *Small Ruminant Lentivirus*
208 infection (Davies et al., 2009), but has not been addressed properly, due to lack of large-scale recording
209 for those diseases.

210

211 3. Genomic basis for mastitis resistance

212

213 3.1. QTL detection

214

215 3.1.1. Primary discovery of QTLs

216 QTL for mastitis resistance have been evidenced in dairy sheep. Among primary QTL detection
217 implemented within the 'Genesheepsafety' EU project, the common mastitis resistance phenotype was
218 milk somatic cell counts, measured periodically over a lactation period. Studies used low-density
219 microsatellite panel (130-181 markers) at the time and only gave a limited resolution of the QTL
220 locations and large chromosomal regions were not covered. One major finding was a QTL on *Ovis aries*

221 chromosome 20 (OAR20), 30cM distant from the MHC (Major Histocompatibility Complex) gene
222 cluster, in a Churra population with 1,421 ewes (Gutiérrez-Gil et al., 2007).

223 The availability of the Illumina OvineSNP50 beadchip, with 54K SNPs in 2009 has allowed
224 undertaking genome-wide association studies to map more precisely loci describing significant genetic
225 variations in mastitis susceptibility. The ‘Sustainable Solutions for Small Ruminants’ (‘3SR’) project
226 has been initiated, with the aim to implement genome scans for traits with high importance for health
227 and sustainability in sheep, including mastitis resistance, and to develop selectable genetic markers and
228 identify the causative mutation(s) where possible. QTL detection for somatic cell counts was performed
229 in three large dairy sheep populations by the consortium in France, Spain, and Italy (Sechi et al., 2013;
230 Rupp et al., 2015; Gutiérrez-Gil et al., 2018). Those populations were as below.

- 231 • 2,414 individuals of a Sardinian Back-cross population, including Back-cross ewes and 10 F1 sires
232 (Sardinian × Lacaune), and Back-cross daughters with their sires (Sechi et al., 2013).
- 233 • 1,598 individuals from Churra daughters family population, including ewes and 16 sires (Gutiérrez-
234 Gil, 2018).
- 235 • 1,009 artificial insemination sires from a Lacaune grand-daughter families, including sons from 33
236 sires (Rupp et al., 2015).

237 QTL detection was implemented using linkage analyses (LA), linkage analyses combined with
238 linkage disequilibrium (LDLA) or linkage disequilibrium (LD) with various software and programs.
239 Latest results from the three studies are summarised in Table 2. Genome-wise significant QTL regions
240 associated with somatic cell counts were found in 21 regions in the Churra population (Gutiérrez-Gil et al.
241 et al., 2013) by LDLA on OAR1, OAR2, OAR3, OAR8, OAR11, OAR13, OAR14, OAR17, OAR18,
242 OAR19, OAR20, OAR22 and OAR25, of which the QTL on OAR20 and 25 were confirmed by linkage
243 analysis. The linkage analysis method highlighted an additional QTL region on OAR5. The OAR20
244 region validated earliest results with microsatellites markers (Gutiérrez-Gil et al., 2007) and was selected
245 for further fine mapping. Sechi et al. (2013) identified seven regions associated with somatic cell counts
246 in the Sardinian BC population on OAR3 (two regions), OAR4, OAR5, OAR12, OAR19, OAR20.
247 Further fine mapping for the most significant regions on OAR4 and OAR20 has been projected. Finally,
248 genome-wise significant QTL regions associated with somatic cell counts were found in five regions in
249 the Lacaune grand-daughter population on OAR3, OAR4, OAR11, OAR16, OAR23 (Rupp et al., 2015).
250 The QTL located on OAR3 exhibited a highly significant threshold and a narrow confidence interval
251 (<0.5 Mb) and was further studied.

252

253 *3.1.2. Fine mapping and identification of a causal mutation associated with mastitis*

254 To fine map the most significant QTLs on OAR3 QTL in Lacaune (Rupp et al., 2015) and OAR20
255 in Churra (Gutiérrez-Gil et al., 2018) ewes, authors subsequently used whole genome sequencing of
256 three animals: a QTL sire and two of his sons with extreme phenotypes. Among candidate causal

257 mutations, Gutiérrez-Gil et al. (2018) detected 13 variants distributed across seven immune-related
258 genes predicted to cause an effect on protein function. The nominated genes were: *PKHD1*, *NOTCH4*,
259 *AGER*, *MOG* and three genes orthologous to the human MHC: *ENSOARG00000009395* (*HLA-C*, *Homo*
260 *sapiens*), *ENSOARG00000015002* (*HLA-B*, *Homo sapiens*) and *ENSOARG00000018075* (*BoLA*, *Bos*
261 *taurus*, orthologous to human *HLA-A*).

262 For the OAR3 region, Rupp et al. (2015) identified a candidate SNP mutation that mapped to the
263 coding sequence of the highly conserved gene *suppressor of cytokine signalling2* (*SOCS2*). An assay
264 for evaluating the protein binding affinity suggested a functional knockout of the *SOCS2* gene in
265 homozygous susceptible sheep. The authors proposed that this mutation altered actual function in the
266 JAK/STAT/SOCS pathway and the control of the inflammatory response to infection. Genetic variants
267 in genes involved in the JAK/STAT/SOCS pathway (*STAT5A* and *JAK2*) were previously associated
268 with mastitis indicator traits (SCC) in Chinese Holstein cattle (Usman et al, 2014), which also supported
269 the importance of this pathway in the determinism of the host's response to mastitis. It has to be noted
270 that Rupp et al. (2015) have further reported a pleiotropic favorable effect of the *SOCS2* mutation on
271 body growth and milk production. This has provided a molecular basis for the antagonism between
272 mastitis resistance and production traits and has highlighted the need for better knowledge on such
273 genetic variants with adverse effects to achieve optimal balancing selection.

274

275 3.1.3. Validation of QTLs in independent populations

276 Generally, QTLs had moderate effects; for the most significant, they explained 3% of the variance
277 for the Churra OAR20 QTL and up to 12% for the Lacaune OAR3 QTL. The QTLs were mostly
278 population specific, in agreement with the polygenic nature of the trait and the complexity of the
279 resistance phenotype. When considering also less significant QTLs though, a few commonalities among
280 populations have been identified, e.g., on OAR12 and OAR20 (Table 2). Accordingly, the 3SR
281 consortium partners designed a public custom-designed ovine SNP chip
282 (http://genoweb.toulouse.inra.fr/~tosser/3SR-WP3-960_snp_mastitis/) for validating the most
283 significant QTL and the common QTL regions in independent populations at the time. The validation
284 chip comprised 960 SNPs distributed over seven genomic regions. SNPs were selected from the
285 OvineSNP50 beadchip or 800K Illumina ovine chips (Nicolazzi et al., 2015) or were identified within
286 the '3SR' project by genome resequencing.

287 Validation studies were performed using this custom chip in three independent dairy sheep
288 populations: Chios (Banos et al., 2017), Lacaune and Manech Red Face ewes (Oget et al., 2019). Banos
289 et al. (2017) confirmed significant QTL associated with four different mastitis related-traits on OAR2,
290 OAR3, OAR5, OAR16 and OAR19; they also highlighted 14 relevant candidate genes implicated in
291 innate immunity in these regions, based on several analyses such as a pathway and functional clustering
292 analysis, a gene expression analysis and a transcription factor binding site analysis. The selected genes
293 included *SOCS2*, *CTLA4*, *C6*, *C7*, *C9*, *PTGER4*, *DAB2*, *CARD6*, *OSMR*, *PLXNC1*, *IDH1*, *ICOS*, *FYB*

294 and *LYFR* (Banos et al., 2017). Oget et al. (2019) validated four of the seven mastitis QTL regions:
295 OAR2 (Lacaune and Manech Red Face), OAR3 (Lacaune), OAR16 (Manech Red Face), OAR19
296 (Lacaune). The point mutation in *SOCS2* (OAR3 QTL region), included in the 960 SNP chip, was the
297 most significant SNP associated with three mastitis related-traits: increased SCS, increased incidence of
298 bacterial infection and mammary abscess. This mutation was also significantly associated with increased
299 body growth, confirming the pleiotropic effect of the *SOCS2* gene. This SNP was not present in the
300 Manech Red Face available data. Two validated regions (OAR2 and 16) were also associated with milk
301 production traits in both populations, indicating, at least in part, a genomic basis for the trade-off
302 between milk production and mastitis resistance. These validation studies testify to the partial sharing
303 of mastitis-related genetic mechanisms between different distant dairy sheep populations.

304

305 3.2. The input on mechanisms from gene expression data

306

307 A number of studies have investigated the host response to mastitis, using gene expression data.
308 The studies were performed on various cell types: milk somatic cells (Bonnetfont et al., 2011), dendritic
309 cells (Genini et al., 2011; Toufeer et al., 2011), mammary epithelial cells (Bonnetfont et al., 2012) or
310 mammary tissue samples (Chopra-Dewasthaly et al., 2017). Cells were exposed either to a microbial
311 agent (*Staphylococcus aureus*, *S. epidermidis*, *Staphylococcus* spp., *Mycoplasma agalactiae*) *in vivo*
312 after an intramammary challenge or to inactivated pathogens or bacterial soluble factors *in vitro* in
313 cultured cells. Up to date, microarrays have mostly been used, either with ovine oligonucleotide
314 (homologous) probes (Bonnetfont et al., 2011, 2012; Toufeer et al., 2011) or bovine cDNA
315 (heterologous) probes (Genini et al., 2011). One publication thus far has used RNAseq profiling
316 (Chopra-Dewasthaly et al., 2017), but it can be anticipated, however, that future studies will use
317 RNASeq analysis, since it gives a more exhaustive view of the transcriptome. In all studies, but the
318 RNAseq profiling, Lacaune ewes from a divergent selection experiment based on somatic cell were
319 used. The main outcomes of these studies were as below.

- 320 • Larger T-cell recruitment after *S. aureus* as compared to *S. epidermidis* challenge was evident.
- 321 • A significant difference was noted in the gene expression profile of milk somatic cells and dendritic
322 cells in the genetic divergent lines, suggesting that they played a major role in genetic
323 resistance/susceptibility, whereas mammary epithelial cells exhibited a more similar profile.
- 324 • Milk somatic cells gene profiling showed several differences between animals from the two divergent
325 lines, suggesting a relationship between immune response and genetic resistance; this included
326 cytokine and chemokine differential expression, a potentially more efficient neutrophil diapedesis, a
327 more efficient clearance of the infection through TLR2 and MAPK signaling pathways, a limitation
328 of cell proliferation and apoptosis in the resistant line.

- 329 • In dendritic cells, resistant animals showed upregulation of complement pathway genes and
330 downregulation of the ILR1 pathway.
- 331 • Transcriptome differences between resistant and susceptible lines were related to transcriptional
332 activity within Milk Somatic Cells. RAR α , TP53, AHR were transcriptional factors of interest, both
333 because of their differential expression and their interaction with a larger number of regulated genes
334 between lines.

335 Interestingly, Banos et al. (2017) used crossed information from QTL detection and several public
336 and in house datasets to propose 14 candidate genes for mastitis. This was based on the assumption that
337 genes contributing to mastitis resistance are likely to be expressed both in the mammary gland and in
338 immune tissues and differentially expressed in sheep bone marrow-derived macrophages in response to
339 lipopolysaccharide administration. This analysis was completed with the study of 1kb upstream regions
340 of the Transcription Factor Binding Sites different in dairy and meat breeds. Further studies are required
341 to confirm the functional impact of the candidate polymorphisms.

342

343 **4. Breeding for improved mastitis resistance**

344

345 *4.1. Selection criteria and breeding objectives*

346

347 Breeding programs in dairy sheep were first developed in the 1960s. Only a few dairy populations
348 worldwide, mainly located in the para-Mediterranean region (Lacaune, Manech, Basco-béarnaise
349 [France], Assaf, Latxa, Manchega, Churra [Spain], Sarda [Italy], Chios [Greece] populations) have the
350 required size and organisation to allow development of large scale recording, genetic evaluation and
351 breeding programmes (Barillet et al., 2001; Carta et al., 2009; Gootwine, 2011; Theodoridis et al., 2018).
352 Milk yield has been the main selection criterion in most of those breeds during the past decades (Carta
353 et al., 2009). Thereafter, in some breeds, a component for milk composition (Barillet et al., 2001;
354 Gutiérrez-Gil et al., 2009) and udder morphology (Casu et al., 2006; Marie-Etancelin et al., 2006) has
355 been added.

356 Following the cattle initiative in the 1980s (Heringstad et al., 2000), in several dairy sheep
357 populations, milk somatic cell counting has been considered as a proxy for mastitis and included that in
358 recording schemes and breeding objectives. Thus, somatic cell counting recording has been
359 implemented in several breeds in France (Lacaune, Manech), Italy (Sarda) and Spain (Churra,
360 Manchega, and Laxta) (Carta et al., 2009). Repeated cell counting data can be routinely recorded as part
361 of milk recording. However, the recording cost per animal, relative to the potential income, is prohibitive
362 for many traits other than production. Therefore, simplified schemes have been developed, with only 2
363 to 4 test days per lactation period or with sampling only in ewes in their first or/and second parity (Rupp
364 et al., 2002; Carta et al., 2009).

365 Up to date, systematic selection for somatic cell counting in addition to milk production and udder
366 morphology is being performed only in Lacaune sheep (Rupp et al., 2002; Barillet et al., 2009). In this
367 breed, the current relative weight for somatic cell counts is 25% in the total merit index, with relative
368 weights of somatic cell scores compared to the production of 1:2. At current selection intensities, such
369 a combination is expected to reduce somatic cell scores by one genetic standard deviation in 10 years.
370 Recently, a genetic evaluation for somatic cell counts has been initiated in Manech Red Face sheep,
371 updating accordingly the breeding objectives. Indirect selection for improved mastitis resistance can be
372 also expected if udder morphology is used for selection, as this gives favorable genetic correlations
373 between traits, as performed in Sarda sheep (Casu et al., 2006).

374 A divergent selection experiment based on somatic cell scores in Lacaune dairy sheep has
375 provided evidence that selection for decreased milk somatic cell counts may help to improve host's
376 resistance to mastitis and decrease the frequency for clinical and subclinical intramammary infections
377 (Rupp et al., 2009; Allain et al., 2010). Based on the results of approx. 200 ewes in each line selected
378 for either high or low somatic cell scores, authors have shown a large difference between the genetic
379 lines for somatic cell counts: mean cell counts were 1,200,000 *versus* 280,000 cells mL⁻¹, respectively.
380 A significant decrease of clinical mastitis, chronic clinical mastitis (as detected by the presence of
381 parenchymal abscesses), and intramammary infections caused by various pathogens (measured by
382 repeated milk bacteriological tests) was also observed in the low somatic cell score line when compared
383 to the high line (Rupp et al., 2009; Allain et al., 2010). The reduced risk of mastitis when selecting for
384 decreased somatic cell scores was further confirmed in two experiments, in which ewes from the
385 divergent lines were challenged with *S. epidermidis* or *S. aureus* (Bonnetfont et al., 2011). The results
386 indicated that selection for decreased somatic cell scores correlated with a better ability to control
387 intramammary multiplication of bacteria and to limit consequences of infection and inflammation.

388 Minor consideration has been given to mastitis in meat sheep industry up to date. However, in a
389 meat breed (Texel), Conington et al. (2008) have highlighted economic and welfare benefits through the
390 reduction of antibiotic use and extra labor involved. These authors estimated that a 10% reduction in
391 risk of developing mastitis would be leading to GBP 8.40 per ewe, or GBP 2.7 million a year to the
392 purebred Texel population in the United Kingdom (Conington et al., 2008; McLaren et al., 2018).
393 Additionally, the authors underlined that increased incidence of subclinical mastitis had an adverse in
394 the body weight of lambs of affected ewes and thus in overall production output of the flock. However,
395 given that in meat-production flocks ewes are not handled on a daily basis, as in dairy flocks, use of
396 somatic cell counts poses challenges. In view of that, McLaren et al. (2018) have suggested results of
397 California Mastitis Test and udder conformation scoring could be useful alternative selection criteria for
398 future genetic selection.

399

400 *4.2. The contribution of genomics to breeding for mastitis resistance*

401

402 4.2.1 Direct use of information from major genes

403 Diagnostic tools can be developed for genotyping major genes, when causal mutation or closely
404 linked markers, are identified. As an example of a disease-related gene, testing for *PrP* gene associated
405 to resistance and susceptibility to scrapie (Elsen et al., 1999), is used in breeding programs worldwide,
406 mainly to avoid entering susceptible animals in the reproduction process. Other significant genes in
407 sheep are *Tmem154*, associated with resistance to *Small Ruminant Lentivirus* infections (Heaton et al.,
408 2012), and *FecL* for hyperprolificacy of ewes (Martin et al., 2014). To date, the large-scale development
409 of such marker-assisted selection for improving mastitis resistance in various sheep populations is
410 unlikely. Indeed, the *SOCS2* gene is the only published causal mutation for mastitis resistance and the
411 susceptible allele was found only in the Lacaune breed (Rupp et al., 2015).

412 Mastitis resistance is highly polygenic with a large number of genes with small effects, which is
413 not well suited for single gene-based selection. With the decrease of sequencing and genotyping costs
414 and the addition of genomic studies in sheep, it is expected, though, that additional causal mutations will
415 be available in the near future. One interesting opportunity is the development of small sets of parentage
416 SNP or low-density chips including also major gene information, which could allow extending such
417 diagnosis approach for various traits and population at reasonable costs.

418

419 4.2.2 Genomic selection

420 The objective of genomic evaluations, called by extension ‘genomic selection’, is to estimate the
421 genetic value (called Estimated Breeding Value, i.e., EBV) of an individual for a given trait (e.g.,
422 mastitis resistance, i.e. somatic cell counts) based on genomic information, such as SNP markers
423 covering the whole genome (Meuwissen et al., 2001). No information on the genes or genomic regions
424 associated with the trait is necessary. Genomic evaluation requires a significant number of genotyped
425 and phenotyped individuals, forming the ‘reference population’, in which associations between SNP and
426 phenotypes are established. Then, using the established predictions, genomic EBVs are estimated in a
427 population of related candidates, for which no phenotype is (yet) available. The benefit from the
428 genomic selection is derived from the fact that genomic EBVs have higher accuracies, i.e. better predict
429 future achieved performance, than pedigree-based EBVs, so that early selection can be efficient. Thus,
430 genomic selection can be useful in sheep breeding to increase the genetic gain by decreasing the
431 generation interval. This is especially true in dairy sheep because there is a long period between the
432 dissemination of male’s semen across the population and collection of phenotypes recorded in female
433 progeny. Genomic selection in ruminants can also be useful for traits that are not measured in large-
434 scale population as a routine, e.g., mastitis in meat sheep breeds.

435 A few studies have compared pedigree-based selection and selection based on genomic
436 information for mastitis resistance (SCS trait) in the Lacaune dairy breed and have reported a gain of
437 prediction accuracy ranging from +0.04 to +0.10 (Duchemin et al., 2012; Baloché et al., 2014). These
438 results are lower than in cattle (+0.15) (VanRaden et al., 2009) probably mainly because reference

439 population is smaller and the genetic diversity is higher, as proven by lower linkage disequilibrium
440 (Baloche et al., 2014). Currently, the so-called Single Step Genomic Best Linear Unbiased Prediction
441 (ssGBLUP) method provides the best accuracies in dairy sheep (Baloche et al., 2014); the model uses
442 raw performances of daughters rather than ram's averages.

443 Future improvement of genomic selection is expected from the inclusion of major genes and
444 QTLs in genomic evaluation models. Indeed, knowledge of genes/genomic regions with a strong effect
445 can be added to the genome-wide SNP panel or added independently as a correlated trait, like in the
446 Gene Content Multiple trait BLUP model (Legarra and Vitezica, 2015). Such approaches have proved to
447 increase prediction accuracy for goat milk composition, with the inclusion of information on the α s1
448 casein (Carillier-Jacquin et al., 2016; Teissier et al., 2018) major genes together with the 50K SNP chip.
449 Application to mastitis resistance, with the inclusion of the *SOCS2* gene or other QTLs, is promising.

450

451 **5. Concluding remarks**

452

453 In this paper, we summarized recent advances in genetic and genomic analyses for the
454 improvement of mastitis resistance in dairy and meat-production sheep. The numerous studies on the
455 correlations between the different traits of interest in these two sheep sectors, as well as the major new
456 genes discovered thanks to the progress of genomic tools, pave the way for a selection of more robust
457 individuals for sustainable breeding.

458

459 **Conflict of interest statement**

460

461 The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

462

463 **Acknowledgments**

464

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467

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Table 1. Estimates of heritabilities for mastitis-related traits and genetic correlations with milk yield and mastitis-related traits in ewes.

Reference (chronological order)	Sheep breed	Number of		Trait	Model	Heritability	Genetic correlations: trait and	
		Records	Ewes				Milk yield	Other mastitis traits
Baro et al., 1994	Churra	10,171 test-days	3,832	Somatic cell scores	Test-day	0.04	-0.37	-
El-Saied et al., 1999	Churra	3,231 lactation periods	2,379	Somatic cell scores	Lactation period	0.12	-0.15	-
Barillet et al., 2001	Lacaune	23,091 test-days	5,272	Somatic cell scores (1 st lactation period)	Lactation period	0.15	0.11	-
Othmane et al., 2002a	Churra	1,962 lactation periods	1,111	Somatic cell scores	Lactation period	0.11	-0.17	-
Othmane et al., 2002b	Churra	7,492 test-days	1,119	Somatic cell scores	Test-day	0.11	-0.36	-
Gonzalo et al., 2003	Churra	4,692 test-days	1,337	Somatic cell scores	Test-day	0.09 - 0.11	-	-
Rupp et al., 2003	Lacaune	273,975 test-days	94,445	Somatic cell scores (1 st lactation period)	Lactation period	0.13	0.18	SCS (2 nd lactation period): 0.93
		131,947 test-days	45,499	Somatic cell scores (2 nd lactation period)		0.12	0.08	SCS (1 st lactation period): 0.93
Serrano et al., 2003	Manchega	37,641 test-days	10,962	Somatic cell scores (1 st lactation period)	Lactation period	0.12	-0.12	-
		36,793 test-days	10,560	Somatic cell scores (2 nd lactation period)		0.19	-0.14	-
		29,358 test-days	8,379	Somatic cell scores (3 rd lactation period)		0.24	-0.15	-
Hamann et al., 2004	East Friesian	9,729 test-days	1,108	Somatic cell scores	Test-day	0.16	0.02	-
Legarra and Ugarte, 2005	Latxa	9,805 lactation periods	6,165	Somatic cell scores	Lactation period	0.13	-0.30	-

Barillet, 2007	Lacaune	121,283 lactation periods	121,283	Somatic cell scores (1 st lactation period)	Lactation period	0.15	0.15	
Riggio et al., 2007	Valle del Belice	13,066 test-days	2,277	Somatic cell scores (1 st lactation period)	Test-day	0.14	0.23	-
Barillet et al., 2009	Manech Red Face	~163,458 test-days	58,378	Somatic cell scores (1 st lactation period)	Lactation period	0.10	0.21	-
Casu et al., 2010	Sarda, Sarda × Lacaune	1,682 test-days	1,587	Somatic cell scores (1 st lactation period)	Lactation period	0.26 - 0.28	-	-
Riggio et al., 2010	Valle del Belice	8,843 test-days	1,120	Somatic cell scores	Test-day	0.09	-	-
				Infection status (bacteriological examination)	Threshold animal	0.09	-	SCS infected / uninfected ewes: 0.81 / 0.51
				Somatic cell scores of infected ewes	Test-day	0.03	-	InfS / SCS uninfected ewes: 0.81, 0.62
				Somatic cell scores of uninfected ewes	Test-day	0.10	-	InfS / SCS infected ewes: 0.51/ 0.62
De la Fuente et al., 2011	Churra	10,189 test-days	3,977	Somatic cell scores	Test-day	0.09	-	-
Tolone et al., 2013	Valle del Belice	17,843 test-days	2,040	Somatic cell scores	Test-day	0.09	-	InfS: 0.93
				Infection status (bacteriological examination)	Threshold animal	0.09	0.59	SCS: 0.93
Tolone et al., 2016	Valle del Belice	5,305 lactation periods	2,350	Infection status (bacteriological examination)	Threshold animal	0.02	-	InfS by cnS / by Str.: 0.92 / 0.36
	Valle del Belice			Infection status by coagulase-negative staphylococci (bacteriological examination)		0.02	-	InfS / InfS by Str: 0.92 / 0.24

	Valle del Belice			Infection status by <i>Streptococcus</i> spp. (bacteriological examination)		0.09	-	InfS / InfS by cnS: 0.36 / 0.24
Banos et al., 2017	Chios	2,436 samples	609	Somatic cell scores (1 st and 2 nd lactation period)	Test-day (week)	0.11	-0.12*	CMT / TBC / Dev c/m: 0.77 / 0.56 / 0.35
				Scores of California Mastitis Test (1 st and 2 nd lactation periods)		0.12	-0.12*	CMT / TBC / Dev c/m: 0.77 / 0.21 / 0.36
				Total bacterial counts (1 st and 2 nd lactation periods)		0.09	-0.11*	SCS / CMT / Dev c/m: 0.56 / 0.21 / 0.35
				Development of clinical mastitis (1 st and 2 nd lactation periods)	Logit function	0.18	-0.09*	SCS / CMT / TBC: 0.35 / 0.36 / 0.35
O'Brien et al., 2017	Belclare, Charollais, Suffolk, Texel, Vendéen	3,378 examinations	3,378	Scores of California Mastitis Test	Linear animal	0.04	-	-
Allain et al., 2018	Lacaune	-	377,945	Somatic cell scores (1 st lactation period)	Lactation period	0.22	0.12	StaphC: 0.72
			518	Staphylococcal counts (1 st lactation period)		0.18	0.31	SCS: 0.72
McLaren et al., 2018	Texel	3,410 samples	2,957	Average somatic cell scores of samples from both mammary glands	Animal model	0.08 - 0.11	-	Sum CMT: 0.76 - 0.96 Max CMT: 0.79 - 0.98
		3,539 samples		Sum of scores of California Mastitis Test in samples from both mammary glands		0.09 - 0.11	-	Av SCS: 0.76 - 0.96 Max CMT: 0.99
		3,529 samples		Maximum score of California Mastitis Test in samples from both mammary glands		0.07 - 0.08	-	Av SCS: 0.79 - 0.98 Sum CMT: 0.99

676 SCS: somatic cell score, InfS: infection status, cnS: coagulase-negative staphylococci, Str.: streptococci, CMT: Scores of California Mastitis Test, TBC: total bacterial
677 counts, Dev c/m: development of clinical mastitis, StaphC: staphylococcal counts, Sum CMT: Sum of scores of California Mastitis Test in samples from both mammary
678 glands, Max CMT: Maximum score of California Mastitis Test in samples from both mammary glands, Av SCS: Average somatic cell scores of samples from both
679 mammary glands.

680 *Results obtained by Banos et al. (pre-print on the BioRxiv platform, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1101/577015>) that use the same samples as in Banos et al. (2017).

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682 **Table 2.** Significant QTL influencing somatic cell scores identified by the Combined Linkage
683 Disequilibrium and Linkage Analysis (LDLA), Linkage Disequilibrium (LD) or Linkage Analysis (LA)
684 in three dairy sheep populations.

OAR	Position (Mb)	Confidence interval	Method	Sheep breed	Reference
1	259.05	-	LDLA	Churra	Gutiérrez-Gil et al., 2018
2	83.10	83.1 - 83.2	LDLA	Churra	Gutiérrez-Gil et al., 2018
	140.36	-	LDLA	Churra	Gutiérrez-Gil et al., 2018
	185.00	185.0 - 185.1	LDLA	Churra	Gutiérrez-Gil et al., 2018
3	4.40	4.3 - 4.4	LDLA	Sarda, Sarda × Lacaune	Sechi et al., 2013
	22.65	22.6 - 22.8	LD	Lacaune	Rupp et al., 2015
	94.40	-	LDLA	Churra	Gutiérrez-Gil et al., 2018
	129.94	129.8 - 130.0	LD	Lacaune	Rupp et al., 2015
	130.10	129.4 - 131.4	LA	Lacaune	Rupp et al., 2015
	184.40	-	LDLA	Churra	Gutiérrez-Gil et al., 2018
	189.57	189.6 - 189.6	LDLA	Sarda, Sarda × Lacaune	Sechi et al., 2013
	212.70	-	LDLA	Churra	Gutiérrez-Gil et al., 2018
4	15.86	15.8 - 16.0	LD	Lacaune	Rupp et al., 2015
	46.99	42.8 - 56.7	LDLA	Sarda, Sarda × Lacaune	Sechi et al., 2013
5	68.69	68.6 - 68.9	LDLA	Sarda, Sarda × Lacaune	Sechi et al., 2013
	77.99	74.9 - 81.5	LA	Churra	Gutiérrez-Gil et al., 2018
	102.69	102.6 - 102.8	LD	Lacaune	Rupp et al., 2015
6	71.31	71.1 - 71.5	LD	Lacaune	Rupp et al., 2015
7	24.53	24.4 - 24.6	LD	Lacaune	Rupp et al., 2015
8	59.85	59.7 - 59.9	LD	Lacaune	Rupp et al., 2015
	80.60	-	LDLA	Churra	Gutiérrez-Gil et al., 2018
	82.60	81.4 - 83.5	LA	Lacaune	Rupp et al., 2015
9	27.49	27.4 - 27.6	LD	Lacaune	Rupp et al., 2015
10	49.30	48.9 - 49.6	LA	Lacaune	Rupp et al., 2015
	74.84	74.7 - 74.9	LD	Lacaune	Rupp et al., 2015
11	36.70	35.8 - 41.1	LA	Lacaune	Rupp et al., 2015
	41.18	41.0 - 41.3	LD	Lacaune	Rupp et al., 2015
	56.78	56.8 - 56.9	LDLA	Churra	Gutiérrez-Gil et al., 2018
12	13.84	13.7 - 13.9	LD	Lacaune	Rupp et al., 2015
	18.43	9.7 - 18.4	LDLA	Sarda, Sarda × Lacaune	Sechi et al., 2013
13	70.89	70.8 - 71.1	LD	Lacaune	Rupp et al., 2015
	71.82	68.5 - 71.8	LDLA	Churra	Gutiérrez-Gil et al., 2018
14	32.00	-	LDLA	Churra	Gutiérrez-Gil et al., 2018
	39.40	36.4 - 40.2	LA	Lacaune	Rupp et al., 2015
	43.28	-	LDLA	Churra	Gutiérrez-Gil et al., 2018
	56.58	56.5 - 56.7	LD	Lacaune	Rupp et al., 2015
16	5.89	5.8 - 6.0	LD	Lacaune	Rupp et al., 2015
	36.10	35.2 - 37.0	LA	Lacaune	Rupp et al., 2015
17	23.65	23.5 - 23.7	LD	Lacaune	Rupp et al., 2015
	33.80	-	LDLA	Churra	Gutiérrez-Gil et al., 2018
	42.30	-	LDLA	Churra	Gutiérrez-Gil et al., 2018
18	12.65	-	LDLA	Churra	Gutiérrez-Gil et al., 2018
	31.18	30.9 - 31.3	LD	Lacaune	Rupp et al., 2015

19	26.17	-	LDLA	Churra	Gutiérrez-Gil et al., 2018
	28.60	28.4-28.7	LD	Lacaune	Rupp et al., 2015
	56.70	56.7-56.78	LDLA	Sarda, Sarda × Lacaune	Sechi et al., 2013
20	5.50	5.4-5.5	LDLA	Churra	Gutiérrez-Gil et al., 2018
	21.52	20.9-23.8	LA	Churra	Gutiérrez-Gil et al., 2018
	23.52	22.0-28.0	LDLA	Churra	Gutiérrez-Gil et al., 2018
	23.75	13.8-25.4	LDLA	Sarda, Sarda × Lacaune	Sechi et al., 2013
22	48.73	48.6-48.8	LD	Lacaune	Rupp et al., 2015
	23.76	-	LDLA	Churra	Gutiérrez-Gil et al., 2018
	48.47	48.4-48.6	LD	Lacaune	Rupp et al., 2015
23	59.94	59.8-60.0	LD	Lacaune	Rupp et al., 2015
24	73.00	7.2-7.4	LD	Lacaune	Rupp et al., 2015
25	16.58	15.6-16.6	LDLA	Churra	Gutiérrez-Gil et al., 2018
	32.50	32.5-35.0	LDLA	Churra	Gutiérrez-Gil et al., 2018
	39.48	38.6-41.7	LA	Churra	Gutiérrez-Gil et al., 2018
26	19.57	19.5-19.7	LD	Lacaune	Rupp et al., 2015